

Benzodiazepine-sparing sedation in adult neurocritical care: effects on delirium and mechanical ventilation outcomes

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Citation

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REVIEW TITLE AND BASIC DETAILS

Review title

Benzodiazepine-sparing sedation in adult neurocritical care: effects on delirium and mechanical ventilation outcomes

Condition or domain being studied

Intensive Care Neurological Disorder; Traumatic Brain Injury; Mechanical ventilation; Benzodiazepine derivatives hypnotics and sedatives; Midazolam; Benzodiazepine; Delirium; Weaning From Mechanically Assisted Ventilation

Neurocritical care sedation strategies in adults with acute brain injury requiring intensive care (e.g., traumatic brain injury, subarachnoid haemorrhage, intracerebral haemorrhage, malignant ischemic stroke, and status epilepticus) who require mechanical ventilation. The review focuses on benzodiazepine exposure as part of sedation management and its association with delirium and ventilation-related outcomes.

Rationale for the review

Sedation is a core component of neurocritical care to facilitate mechanical ventilation, control agitation, and support intracranial pressure (ICP) management. Benzodiazepines remain widely used in many ICUs, yet in general critical care settings benzodiazepine exposure has been associated with adverse neurocognitive outcomes, including delirium, and may prolong mechanical ventilation. However, patients with acute brain injury represent a distinct population in whom sedation depth, neurological assessment constraints, and ICP/ICP targets may influence both sedative choice and outcomes. Evidence specific to neurocritical care comparing benzodiazepine-sparing strategies with benzodiazepine-based regimens remains fragmented across heterogeneous study designs and diagnoses. A systematic review is needed to synthesize current evidence on whether benzodiazepine-sparing sedation is associated with reduced delirium and improved ventilation outcomes in adult neurocritical care.

Review objectives

To systematically review and, where appropriate, meta-analyse evidence comparing benzodiazepine-sparing sedation strategies versus benzodiazepine-based sedation in mechanically ventilated adult neurocritical care patients with acute brain injury, with the primary outcomes of (1) delirium incidence and/or duration and (2) mechanical ventilation outcomes (ventilator-free days and/or duration of mechanical ventilation). Secondary objectives include assessing ICU/hospital length of stay, mortality, extubation failure/reintubation, tracheostomy, sedation target attainment, and key adverse events (e.g., hypotension, bradycardia).

Keywords

Neurocritical care; Neurointensive care; Sedation; Benzodiazepine-sparing; Midazolam; Propofol; Dexmedetomidine; Delirium; Mechanical ventilation; Weaning from mechanical ventilation; Extubation; Traumatic brain injury; Intracranial hemorrhage

Country

Indonesia

ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

Population

Included

Inclusion:

Adults (≥ 18 years) admitted to neurocritical care / ICU with acute brain injury requiring mechanical ventilation and continuous/intermittent ICU sedation. Eligible diagnoses include (but are not limited to): traumatic brain injury (moderate–severe), subarachnoid haemorrhage, intracerebral/intraventricular haemorrhage, malignant ischaemic stroke with cerebral oedema, and status epilepticus requiring ICU-level sedation.

Excluded

Exclusion:

Paediatric populations (<18 years), elective short procedural sedation only (e.g., imaging/procedures without ongoing ICU sedation), patients not requiring mechanical ventilation, and studies in mixed ICU populations without separate extractable neurocritical/acute brain injury data.

Intervention(s) or exposure(s)*Included*

Sedation; Analgesics; Propofol; Dexmedetomidine

Benzodiazepine-sparing sedation is defined as a sedation strategy where benzodiazepines are avoided or minimised as the primary sedative agent. Eligible strategies include propofol- or dexmedetomidine-dominant regimens (with or without opioid-based analgesedation and/or adjuncts), and/or protocolised sedation pathways explicitly restricting continuous benzodiazepine infusions. Studies will be eligible if they report a clear between-group difference in benzodiazepine exposure (e.g., lower cumulative dose, shorter infusion duration, or lower proportion receiving continuous benzodiazepine infusion) and are conducted in mechanically ventilated adult neurocritical care patients.

Excluded

Studies will be excluded if sedation exposure is not clearly defined or cannot be classified as benzodiazepine-sparing versus benzodiazepine-based (e.g., no information on primary sedative agent(s), dosing, duration, or proportion receiving continuous benzodiazepine infusions). We will exclude studies evaluating only brief procedural sedation (e.g., for imaging or short procedures) without ongoing ICU sedation, and studies where benzodiazepines are used solely for indications other than sedation strategy (e.g., single-dose anticonvulsant rescue) without quantifiable sedation exposure. Studies focusing exclusively on anaesthesia for surgery without subsequent ICU sedation management will be excluded. We will also exclude studies of barbiturate coma/burst-suppression protocols as the primary sedation strategy (unless explicitly compared within a benzodiazepine-sparing framework with extractable data), and studies where sedation is confounded by mandatory deep sedation with continuous neuromuscular blockade and outcomes cannot be attributed to sedation strategy.

Comparator(s) or control(s)*Included*

PICO tags selected: Benzodiazepine; Midazolam; Loop diuretic; Diazepam; Usual Care; Sedation

Comparator(s) will include benzodiazepine-based sedation strategies (e.g., continuous midazolam/lorazepam infusion as the primary sedative) or usual/standard care with higher benzodiazepine exposure than the benzodiazepine-sparing group. Studies will be eligible if

between-group benzodiazepine exposure is clearly different (e.g., cumulative dose, infusion duration, or proportion receiving continuous benzodiazepine infusion).

Excluded

Studies will be excluded if the comparator group cannot be clearly classified as benzodiazepine-based sedation or as usual/standard care with higher benzodiazepine exposure than the intervention group. This includes studies where both groups have similar benzodiazepine exposure (no meaningful between-group difference), where benzodiazepines are used only as intermittent rescue doses without quantifiable exposure, or where comparator sedation regimens are insufficiently described (no data on primary sedative agent(s), dosing, duration, or proportion receiving continuous benzodiazepine infusions). Studies in which the comparator consists solely of brief procedural sedation rather than ongoing ICU sedation management will be excluded. If co-interventions (e.g., mandatory deep sedation with continuous neuromuscular blockade, barbiturate coma/burst-suppression protocols) dominate the sedation strategy and prevent attribution of outcomes to benzodiazepine exposure differences, the study will be excluded unless stratified or extractable data are available.

Study design

Both randomized and nonrandomized study types will be included.

Included

Inclusion: Randomised controlled trials, quasi-randomised trials, non-randomised interventional studies, prospective/retrospective cohort studies, and controlled before–after studies with a clear comparator.

Excluded

Exclusion: Case reports, case series without a comparator, narrative reviews, editorials, conference abstracts without sufficient outcome data (unless full data are obtainable), and animal studies.

Context

Studies conducted in adult intensive care units, specifically neuro-ICU/neurocritical care units or mixed ICUs where neurocritical/acute brain injury patients are clearly identified and data are extractable. Sedation must be delivered for ICU care (e.g., ventilation facilitation, agitation control, ICP/ CPP management, status epilepticus management) rather than brief procedural sedation.

TIMELINE OF THE REVIEW

Date of first submission to PROSPERO

04 February 2026

Review timeline

Start date: 3 February 2026. End date: 8 August 2026.

Date of registration in PROSPERO

04 February 2026

AVAILABILITY OF FULL PROTOCOL

Availability of full protocol

A full protocol has been written but is not available because:

The full protocol is currently undergoing internal review and finalisation. It will be made publicly available prior to study selection (e.g., via an open repository).

SEARCHING AND SCREENING

Search for unpublished studies

Only unpublished studies will be sought.

Main bibliographic databases that will be searched

The main databases to be searched are *CENTRAL - Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials, Embase.com, MEDLINE, PubMed* and *Scopus*.

Search language restrictions

There are no language restrictions.

Search date restrictions

Databases will be searched for articles published from 1 January 2010 and before by 1 February 2026.

Other methods of identifying studies

Other studies will be identified by: *reference list checking (backward citation searching)*.

Additional information about identifying studies

We will screen reference lists of included studies and relevant reviews, perform forward citation tracking (e.g., via Scopus/Web of Science/Google Scholar), and hand-search key neurocritical care and critical care journals where appropriate.

Link to search strategy

A full search strategy is available in the full protocol as described in the *Availability of full protocol* section

Selection process

Studies will be screened independently by at least two people (or person/machine combination) with a process to resolve differences.

Other relevant information about searching and screening

Search results will be imported into a reference manager and de-duplicated prior to screening. Screening will be performed using a structured form, piloted on a sample of records to ensure consistency. Where multiple reports describe the same study, data will be collated and treated as a single study.

DATA COLLECTION PROCESS

Data extraction from published articles and reports

Data will be extracted independently by at least two people (or person/machine combination) with a process to resolve differences.

Authors will be asked to provide any required data not available in published reports.

Study datasets/IPD will be obtained from study investigators or via a data repository

We will contact corresponding authors of eligible studies to request de-identified IPD or additional aggregate data where needed. We will also check trial registries and public repositories for available datasets. If IPD cannot be obtained, analyses will proceed using published summary data.

Study risk of bias or quality assessment

Risk of bias will be assessed using: *Cochrane RoB-2* and *ROBINS-I*

Data will be assessed independently by at least two people (or person/machine combination) with a process to resolve differences.

Additional information will be sought from study investigators if required information is unclear or unavailable in the study publications/reports.

Reporting bias assessment

If at least 10 studies are available for a given meta-analysis, publication bias/small-study effects will be assessed using funnel plots and, where appropriate, Egger's test. Selective outcome reporting will be assessed by comparing outcomes specified in methods sections (and trial registry records where available) with reported outcomes.

Certainty assessment

The certainty of evidence for key outcomes (delirium incidence/duration and ventilator-free days and/or duration of mechanical ventilation) will be assessed using the GRADE approach. Two reviewers will rate certainty across risk of bias, inconsistency, indirectness, imprecision, and publication bias, and summarise findings in a 'Summary of Findings' table.

OUTCOMES TO BE ANALYSED

Main outcomes

Delirium: incidence and/or duration during ICU stay, assessed using validated tools (e.g., CAM-ICU, ICDSC) or clinically diagnosed delirium where clearly defined.

Mechanical ventilation outcomes: ventilator-free days (e.g., day 28) and/or duration of mechanical ventilation (days) (including time to successful extubation where reported).

Additional outcomes

Extubation outcomes: extubation failure, reintubation, need for tracheostomy.

Length of stay: ICU length of stay and hospital length of stay.

Mortality: ICU mortality, in-hospital mortality, and/or 28-day mortality (as reported).

Sedation quality: achievement of sedation targets (e.g., proportion of time within target RASS/SAS), over-sedation/under-sedation events.

Adverse events: hypotension, bradycardia, need for vasopressors, and other sedative-related complications as reported.

Neurological outcomes (if available): functional outcome scales such as GOS/GOSE or modified Rankin Scale (mRS) at the longest reported follow-up.

PLANNED DATA SYNTHESIS

Strategy for data synthesis

Where data are sufficiently homogeneous, we will perform quantitative synthesis (meta-analysis). For dichotomous outcomes (e.g., delirium incidence, reintubation, tracheostomy, mortality), we will calculate pooled effect estimates as risk ratios (RR) with 95% confidence intervals (CI) (or odds ratios if required by reporting). For continuous outcomes (e.g., duration of mechanical ventilation, ventilator-free days, delirium duration, ICU/hospital length of stay), we will use mean differences (MD) with 95% CI; if outcomes are measured using different scales or definitions, we will use standardised mean differences (SMD). If time-to-event outcomes are reported, hazard ratios will be synthesised when available. We anticipate clinical and methodological heterogeneity across neurocritical care diagnoses and sedation protocols; therefore, random-effects models will be used as the primary approach (with fixed-effect analyses explored in sensitivity analyses where appropriate). Statistical heterogeneity will be assessed using the I^2 statistic and τ^2 , and explored through pre-specified subgroup analyses (e.g., diagnosis: TBI vs SAH vs ICH vs status epilepticus; sedation depth/targets; presence of ICP monitoring; and dominant sedative strategy such as propofol- vs dexmedetomid

CURRENT REVIEW STAGE

Stage of the review at this submission

Review stage	Started	Completed
Pilot work		
Formal searching/study identification		
Screening search results against inclusion criteria		
Data extraction or receipt of IPD		
Risk of bias/quality assessment		
Data synthesis		

Review status

The review is currently planned or ongoing.

Publication of review results

Results of the review will be published in English and Indonesian.

REVIEW AFFILIATION, FUNDING AND PEER REVIEW

Review team members

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No conflict of interest declared.

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No conflict of interest declared.

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No conflict of interest declared.

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Funding source

Review has no specific/external funding but is supported by guarantor/review team (non-commercial) institutions.

Additional information about funding

No external funding was received. The review will be supported by institutional resources from Universitas Udayana and RSUP Prof. Dr. I.G.N.G. Ngoerah. Funders have no role in the design, conduct, analysis, or publication decisions.

Peer review

The full protocol was internally peer reviewed prior to commencing study selection. Feedback was obtained from an independent neurocritical care clinician and a methodological/statistical advisor not involved in the day-to-day review conduct. Revisions were made to clarify eligibility criteria, outcome definitions (delirium and ventilation outcomes), and the planned approach to risk of bias assessment, synthesis, and GRADE. Any further amendments will be documented and reported transparently.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Additional information

This review will follow PRISMA 2020 reporting guidance. Where meta-analysis is not appropriate due to clinical or methodological heterogeneity, findings will be synthesised narratively with structured tables. Any deviations from the protocol will be documented with rationale and dated amendments.

Review conflict of interest

Declared individual interests are recorded under team member details.. No additional interests are recorded for this review.

Medical Subject Headings

Critical Care; Intensive Care Units; Brain Injuries; Brain Injuries, Traumatic; Intracranial Hemorrhages; Subarachnoid Hemorrhage; Status Epilepticus; Benzodiazepines; Midazolam; Conscious Sedation; Delirium; Respiration; Dexmedetomidine; Propofol

SIMILAR REVIEWS

Check for similar records already in PROSPERO

PROSPERO identified a number of existing PROSPERO records that were similar to this one (last check made on 3 February 2026). These are shown below along with the reasons given by that the review team for the reviews being different and/or proceeding.

- Dexmedetomidine- or Clonidine-Based Sedation Versus Propofol or Benzodiazepines in Critically Ill Patients: An Updated Meta-Analysis of Randomized Controlled Trials [published 2 July 2025] [CRD420251084462]. The review was judged **not to be similar**
- Delirium in Mechanically Ventilated Adults Receiving α_2 -Agonists Versus Propofol or Benzodiazepines for ICU Sedation: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis [published 7 January 2026] [CRD420251238144]. The review was judged **not to be similar**
- Dexmedetomidine versus other sedatives for prevention of delirium in elderly ICU patients: a systematic review and meta-analysis [published 21 September 2025] [CRD420251141987]. The review was judged **not to be similar**

PROSPERO version history

- [Version 1.0, published 04 Feb 2026](#)

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Any enquiries about the record should be referred to the named review contact